

ALANINE KINASE ACTIVITY IN *Heterobranchus bidorsalis* JUVENILES FED DIETS WITH GRADED CONCENTRATIONS OF UNPROCESSED SOYABEAN MEAL

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ABSTRACT

The Alanine Kinase activities in *Heterobranchus bidorsalis juveniles* (14.57 ± 0.44g) fed with five graded concentrations (10.00, 20.00, 30.00, 40.00 and 50.00%) of dietary unprocessed soyabean meal (USBM) and a control (0.00% USBM) for 56 days were studied. Significant increases ($P < 0.05$; $P < 0.01$) in the serum alanine kinase (SAK) and hepatic cytosolic alanine kinase (HCAK) activities in the fish were dependent on the concentration of USBM in the diets. This result is consistent with the reports of other workers: especially on enzymatic responses to the infiltration of extraneous substances into the blood and liver tissues. Increases in SAK and HCAK activities between days 14 and 56 of the study imply that time affected the activities of alanine kinase both in the blood serum and in the liver tissues. It was apparent from the result that the USBM, not only exerted its anti-trypsin pressure on the ultimate protein digestion, absorption and turn-over in the fish as established by previous workers; but facilitated the activities of alanine kinase in its glycolytic phosphorylation potentials and consequent energy metabolism of the fish.

Keywords: *Heterobranchus bidorsalis*, Alanine Kinase, Unprocessed soyabean meal, Blood serum, Hepatic cytosolic.

INTRODUCTION

A fish viscus is known to be a rich source of enzymes, many of which present high activity at low concentrations. Fish digestive enzymes exhibit optimal activity at temperatures much higher than the ambient temperature of fish (Fereidon and Janak-Kamil, 2001). Yasunaga (1972) identified protease activity from digestive organs of three flatfish species namely: the marbled flounder (*Psuedoplueronectes yotcohamae* Gunther, 1877), the stone flounder (*Platichthys bicoloratas* Basilewsky, 1855) and the olive founder (*Paralichthys olivaceus* Temminck and Schlegel, 1846). The author reported an optimum pH of 8.00 and maximal activity at a temperature of 40 C for the flatfishes. Overnell (1973) observed and compared the activities of such enzymes as trypsin, chymotrypsin, carboxypeptidases A and B, leucine, aminopeptidase, ribonuclease, amylase acid phosphatase and alkaline phosphatase. Uys and Hecht (1987) also characterized the activities of pancreatic enzymes including trypsin from the sharp tooth catfish, *Clarias gariepinus* (Burchell, 1822). The workers reported that trypsin displayed optimal activity at pH 8.20 and temperatures ranging from 30°C to 40°C.

The first changes to proteolytic activity in the gut of catfish larvae are rapid and indicate fast enzyme secretions and utilization in response to food ingestion (Pederson *et al.*, 1987; Ueberschar, 1993). Rapid responses of digestive enzymes to food intake are in accordance with the hypothesis that larval digestion and assimilation of nutrients must be highly efficient to ensure high growth rates. However, the decrease in enzyme activity in the sharptooth catfish (*Clarias gariepinus*) in the first 60 min after feeding was probably due to the immediate utilization of enzymes present in the larval intestine at the moment of food injection for protein hydrolysis, (Ueberschar, 1993).

Traditionally, animal protein is regarded as the foundation of any aquaculture feed formulation programme. The utility of such plant proteins as the processed soyabean meal (SBM) has been adequately recognized because of its high digestibility and ample indispensable amino acids (Edwin and Tom, 1995). The unprocessed soyabean

meal (USBM), on the other hand, has anti-nutritional factors that affect catfish growth and performance (Rackis and Liener, 1998). Smith therefore stated that for maximum metabolizable energy in fish, unprocessed soyabean meal should be processed at a minimum temperature of 175°C. Against this background, this study presents the results of the activity of alanine kinase in *Heterobranchus bidorsalis* juveniles fed diets with graded concentrations of unprocessed soyabean meal. The essence of this investigation was to determine the impact of incorporating various concentrations of unprocessed soyabean meal in catfish diets on the activities of alanine kinase necessary for the energy metabolism of this highly priced fish in Nigeria.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Experimental Procedure

Three hundred and sixty (360) juveniles of *Heterobranchus bidorsalis* (mean weight, 14.56 ±0.44g) were transported from Otor-Oweh Aquaculture Centre, Delta State, Nigeria to the Fisheries Laboratory of Ebonyi State University, Abakaliki, Nigeria. The fish specimens were acclimatized for 14 days on a chick starter diet administered at 3% body weight per day (bw.d⁻¹). Records of fish weight were taken with a top-loading electronic Mettler balance (Model PT 600). The fishes were randomly stocked in 18 aerator-equipped glass aquaria (55 x 30 x 30cm³) at 20 fish per aquarium and inundated with 25cm³ dechlorinated tap water. The experiment was designed to have six sets of aquaria, replicated thrice (6 x 3) to provide 18 experimental treatments. Five (5) test diets (D₁, D₂, D₃, D₄, and D₅) were formulated at 38% crude protein (Table 1) to include 5 levels: 10.00, 20.00, 30.00, 40.00 and 50.00% of unprocessed soyabean meal (USBM) respectively. These 5 levels represented the inclusion levels of the unprocessed soyabean as percent replacements of the processed soyabean meal in the control diet (D₁).

Dietary ingredients (Table 1) were thoroughly mixed, precooked and pelletized with a locally fabricated pelletizer and oven-dried. The diets were packed in small cellophane bags, labeled according to dietary treatments and stored in a pest-free cupboard within the laboratory. Proximate analyses of the test diets (D₁-D₅) and the control (D₀) were carried out. Feeding was done thrice daily at 4-hourly intervals (8am, 12noon, and 4pm) at 5% bw.d⁻¹ for 56 days. Water temperature readings (26 ± 0.52 °C) and pH values (6.80 + 0.12) were recorded with a maximum and minimum thermometer and a pH meter (Model Ph-J- 201L) respectively. Control weighing was carried out every 14 days and the feed administered adjusted in accordance with the body weight of fish.

Methods of Feed Analysis

The five USBM incorporated diets (D₁ – D₅) and the control (D₀) were analyzed in the laboratory for their proximate compositions (Table 2) in accordance with Windham (1996) method. The percent nitrogen content was determined by the micro-kjeldahl method and converted to total protein equivalent by multiplying by 6.25 (Windham, 1996). The crude fat was measured in a soxhlet apparatus of lipid by petroleum ether (b.pt. 40-60 °C) extraction. The moisture content was determined by drying 2.00g triplicate samples at 105 °C to constant weight and calculating the percentage moisture by using the formula:

$$\frac{X-Y}{X} \times 100$$

where X = weight of wet sample; Y= dry weight of sample. Ash was determined by combusting 2.00g sample for 12hours at 550°C. The percentage of nitrogen free extract (NFE) was determined by subtractions.

Alanine Kinase Analysis

Blood and liver samples of fish from each triplicate treatment of unprocessed soyabean meal (USBM) and the control were collected and used for assays of the alanine kinase enzyme. The blood samples were collected by both the cardiac puncture method and the severance of the caudal peduncle using disposable hypodermic syringe (Oluah, 1999). The liver was excised and washed in distilled water to remove traces of blood. The liver samples were macerated and homogenized as described by Devi *et al.*(1993) and then placed in ice-cold 0.25 M sucrose (Oluah *et al.*, 2005). The liver homogenate was centrifuged at 5000 rpm for 15 minutes at 4 °C and the supernatant was transferred into clean microfuge tubes. The samples were stored in -80 °C until enzymatic assays were carried out (Ozmen *et al.*, 2005). The blood was similarly centrifuged for 15 minutes at 1000 rpm to obtain the serum. The serum was also stored at -80°C in clean microfuged tubes.

Total protein concentrations of the liver supernatants and blood serum were determined by the methods described by Lowry *et al.* (1951) and using BSA as the standard at 695 nm. Blood serum alanine kinase (SAK) and hepatic cytosolic alanine kinase (HCAK) activities were determined. All enzymatic assays were conducted spectrophotometrically at appropriate wavelengths using microplate reader system (VersaMax Molecular Device Corps., USA) at 25 °C. Samples were assayed in triplicates and data collected analyzed by analysis of variance (ANOVA) to indicate statistical significance ($P < 0.05$). The Duncan's (1955) Multiple Range Test was employed to partition the differences of sampled means. Simple percentages were applied where appropriate to explain the analyzed data.

RESULTS

Table 1 shows the gross compositions of the diets incorporated with the unprocessed soyabean meal (USBM) (D_1 - D_5) and the control (D_0). Table 2 shows the proximate compositions of the six diets while Table 3 shows the serum and hepatic cytosolic alanine kinase activity in the experimental fish. The mortality and survival records of the fish within the 56 days study period are shown in Table 5. The control fish recorded significantly ($P < 0.05$; $P < 0.01$) lower values of serum alanine kinase (SAK)(19.14 ± 0.11 to 22.46 ± 0.13 IU.L⁻¹) and hepatic cytosolic alanine kinase (HCAK)(23.28 ± 0.14 to 26.95 ± 0.14 IU.mg⁻¹) activities than those fed with the USBM incorporated diets (D_1 - D_5)(Table 3). SAK and HCAK values in the fish blood and liver increased significantly ($P < 0.05$; $P < 0.01$) as the quantity of USBM incorporation in the diets increased from 10.00 to 50.00% (Table 3). Furthermore, alanine kinase activities in the fish blood (SAK) and in the liver (HCAK) increased as the blood and liver samples were analyzed on days 14, 28, 41 and 56. Increases in SAK and HCAK values in the fish were recorded between days 14 and 28 irrespective of the percent incorporation of USBM in the diets (Table 3).

The highest SAK value (185.97 ± 0.26 IU. L⁻¹) and HCAK value (227.16 ± 0.27 IU.mg⁻¹) (Table 3) were recorded at day 56 when the fish diet was incorporated with 50% USBM (D_5) as replacement for the processed soyabean meal (SBM) in the control diet (D_0). Conversely, the lowest SAK value (19.14 ± 0.11 IU.L⁻¹) and HCAK value (23.28 ± 0.14 IU. mg⁻¹) were recorded at day 14 when the diet was incorporated with 10% USBM (D_1) as replacement for the SBM in the control diet (D_0). Generally there were consistent increases in SAK and HCAK values in the fish between days 14 and 56 irrespective of the dietary treatment ($D_0 - D_5$) applied.

The percent mortality of fish fed with the control (D_0) was generally lower than those fed with the USBM incorporated diets ($D_1 - D_5$) (Table 4). This situation resulted in more survivals of the *H. bidorsalis* juveniles when fed the SBM control diet than when fed the USBM incorporated diets. However, the impact of the USBM diets on the fish was apparently more pronounced when 40% (D_4) and 50% (D_5) of the SBM in the control (D_0) were replaced with USBM in the formulation (Table 3). This situation also resulted in comparatively lower survivals of fish fed with diets D_5 when the percent survivals were estimated at days 14, 28, 42 and 56 than when fed with diets D_1 , D_2 , D_3 and D_0 (Control) (Table 4).

DISCUSSION

The physiological effects of incorporating the unprocessed soyabean meal (USBM) in the diets led to *H. bidorsalis* juveniles in this study apparently indicated that the USBM affected the activities of other endogenous enzymes in the fish apart from its anti-trypsin attributes (Rackis and Liener, 1998). When soyabean meal is fed raw and unprocessed to catfish, the negative effect of this action on fish performance has been attributed to the presence of anti nutritional factors inimical to fish growth (Rackis and Liener, 1998). Therefore, fish nutritionist are constrained to use the method provided by Smith (1999) to ensure that soyabean meal is processed at a minimum temperature of 175°C before being incorporated into fish diets.

The results of our study indicated the consequences of the unconventional application of unprocessed soyabean meal at different concentrations in catfish diet: especially as it affects the serum and hepatic cytosolic alanine kinase activities. Significant increases ($P < 0.05$; $P < 0.01$) in the values of SAK and HCAK in the fish as the dietary USBM levels increased (Table 3) indicated that the activities of alanine kinase both in the blood and in the liver tissues, were moderated by the quantity of USBM in the diet. These results are at variance with the report of Stiffens (1989) which stated that the unprocessed soyabean meal could hinder the provision of amino acids necessary for growth and production of enzymes. The reasons for this anomaly cannot be explained from this study. However, increased alanine kinase activities as the dietary USBM increased implies that more of this enzyme was synthesized to participate in the glycolytic energy metabolism of the fish as the experiment

progressed from day 14 to day 56. Hence, the USBM not only exerted its anti-trypsin pressure on the ultimate protein digestion, absorption and turn-over by the fish (Rackis and Liener, 1998) but facilitated the activities of alanine kinase enzyme in its glycolytic phosphorylation potentials and consequent energy metabolism of the fish.

Increase in SAK and HCAK activities in the fish as the experiment progressed from day 14 to 56 also implies that time affected the activities of alanine kinase both in the blood serum and in the liver tissues (Table 3). These results are consistent with the report of Oluah *et al.* (2005) which stated that liver lactate dehydrogenase (LDH) activity increased within *Clarias albopunctatus* exposed to sublethal Gammalin 20 and Actellic 25EC concentrations. Similarly, increased SAK and HCAK activities in this study as the dietary USBM concentration increased agree with the report of Oluah *et al.* (2005). The workers postulated that increased LDH activity in *C. albopunctatus* was dependent on the concentration of Gammalin 20 and Actellic 25EC to which the fish was exposed. Other workers reported various enzyme responses due to the infiltration of extraneous substances into the fish blood and liver tissues. Devi *et al.* (1993) reported an increased muscular LDH activity in the brook trout, *Salvelinus fontinalis* and the fiddler crab, *Uca pugilator* exposed to cadmium. Galio and Lawryk (1991) also reported that parathion elicited increased LDH activity in rat; while lindane caused a two-fold increase in liver myloperoxidase activity in rat (Junge *et al.*, 2001).

It could be summarized from this study that SAK and HCAK activities in *H. bidorsalis* juveniles followed a similar pattern relative to the control (Do) when graded concentrations of USBM (D₁ – D₅) were incorporated in the diets fed to the fish. Changes in enzymatic activities vis-a-vis enzyme synthesis probably resulted from the presence of extraneous substance inhibitors (USBM), which might have altered the physiological processes within the fish. Changes in the activity of tissue glycogen and glucose modulating enzymes have been reported in common carp (*Cyprinus carpio*) exposed to paraquat (Simon *et al.*, 1985). Hence, it is quite probable that the consequences of soyabean trypsin-inhibitor (Rackis and Liener, 1998) on the activities of alanine kinase in the fish are quite enormous. The consistent increases in the values of SAK and HCAK from day 14 to day 56 irrespective of the dietary USBM (Table 3) attest to the physiological interference of this USBM based diet on the activities of alanine kinase enzyme. This situation must have resulted in the highest percent mortality (20%) of the fish when fed diet D₅ (50% USBM) up to day 56 (Table 4). The implication of this mortality record is that time might determine the percent mortality of *H. bidorsalis* juveniles subjected to diet incorporated with unprocessed soyabean meal in aquaculture systems.

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Table 1 Gross composition of unprocessed soyabean meal incorporated diets (38% crude protein) fed to *H. bidorsalis* juveniles for 56 days

← Unprocessed Soyabean Meal Incorporated Diets →						
Ingredients	10% USBM ¹	D2 20% USBM	D ₃ 30% USBM	D ₄ 40% USBM	D5 50% USBM	Do 0% USBM Control
Yellow Maize	11.61	11.61	11.61	11.61	11.61	11.61
Unprocessed soyabean meal	5.48	10.95	16.43	21.87	27.30	54.76**
Groundnut cake	49.28	43.81	38.33	32.89	27.46	-
Fish meal	16.43	16.33	16.43	16.43	16.43	16.43
Blood meal	10.95	10.95	10.95	10.95	10.95	10.95
Palm Oil	5.00	5.00	5.00	5.00	5.00	5.00
Salt	0.25	0.25	0.25	0.25	0.25	0.25
Vitamin mit	0.60	0.60	0.60	0.60	0.60	0.60
Mineral mix ¹	0.40	0.40	0.40	0.40	0.40	0.40
	100.00	100.00	100.00	100.00	100.00	100.00

**Unprocessed soyabean meal. Vitamin mix provided the following constituents diluted in cellulose (mg/kg of diet): thiamine. 10; riboflavin, 20; pyridoxine, 10; folacin, 5; pantothenic acid, 40; choline chloride, 3000; niacin, 150; vitamin B12, 0.06; retinyl acetate (500.000 u/g) 12; alpha tocopherol. 50; cholecalciferol (1.000.000.u./g), 6; menaione-Na-bisul phate, 80; inositol. 400; biotin. 2; vitamin C, 200; and ethoxyquine, 200.

³Contained as g/kg of premix: FeSO₄ 7H₂O. 5; MgSO₄. 7H₂O. 132; K₂SO₄, 329.90; KI, 0.15; NaCl, 45; Na₂ SO₄, 44.88; AlCl₃, 0.15; CoCl₂. 5H₂O, 5; CuSO₄. 5H₂O, 5; NaSe O₃, 0.11; MnSO₄. H₂O, 0.07; and cellulose, 380.97.

Value of processed soyabean meal in the contol diet.

Table 2. Proximate composition of unprocessed soyabean meal incorporated diets (38% crude protein) fed to *H. bidorsalis* juveniles for 56 days.

Nutrients	Unprocessed Soyabean Meal incorporated Diets					
	D ₁ (10.00% USBM ¹)	D ₂ (20.00%, USBM)	D ₃ (30.00% USBM)	D ₄ (40.00% USBM)	D ₅ (50.00% USBM)	Do Control (0.00% USBM)
•#						
Crude protein (%) Ether extract (%)	36.83 4.60	36.84 5.03	37.52 5.63	37.60 4.58	37.64 4.56	37.66 5.44
Moisture content	11.52	11.60	11.80	10.58	10.60	11.64
/0\ *	10.51	10.62	10.55	11.46	11.46	10.58
Ash content (%)	36.54	35.91	34.50	35.78	35/74	34.68
NFE ² (%)						
Total	100.00	100.00	100.00	100.00	100.00	100.00

Unprocessed soyabean meal; Nitrogen free extract.

Table 3. Serum and hepatic cytosolic alanine kinase activity in *H. bidorsalis* juveniles fed diets (38% crude protein) incorporated with different concentrations of unprocessed soyabean meal (USBM) for 56 days

Percentage dietary unprocessed soyabean meal (USBM) (°/ o)												
Duration (days)	Do (Control) 0.00% USBM		D ₁ 10.00% USBM		D ₂ 20.00% USBM		D ₃ 30.00% USBM		D ₄ 40.00% USBM		D ₅ 50.00% USBM	
	"SAK^	HCAK-	SAK	HCAK	SAK	HCAK	SAK	HCAK	SAK	HCAK	SAK	HCAK
14	19.14 + o.n ^a	23.28 - 0.0.14 ¹¹	28.52 ^0.14 ^C	34.22 ^0.17 ^d	39.93 - 0.15 ^C	47.91 + 0.17 ^f	54.91 + 0.19 ^s	67.07 + 0.20 ^h	76.87 + 0.23 ¹	93.90 ±0.19'	107.62 ± 0.22 ^k	131.46 ± 0.20 ¹
28	20.37 + 0.12 ^a	24.44 ±0.13 ^{fa}	34.22 + 0.16 ^o	41.06 + 0.16 ^d	47.92 + 0.18 ^C	57.49 + 0.22 ^f	65.89 f 0.21 ^s	80.48 + 0.23 ¹¹	92.24 + 0.24 ¹	112.68 + 0.18-'	129.14 ±0.25 ^k	157.75 zO- 21 ¹
42	21.39 + 0.11 ^y	25.67 + 0.15 ^h	41.07 + 0.15 ^C	49.28 + 0.15 ["]	57.50 + 0.21 ^C	69.99 + 0.23 ^f	79.07 + 0.24 ^g	96.58 ^0.25 ^h	110.69 ±0.14*	135.22 + 0.19 ¹	154.97 - 0.24 ^k	189.30 ± 0.26 ¹
56	22.46 + 0.13 ["]	26.95 ±0.14 ^b	49.28 + 0.16 ^C	59.13 ± 0.20 ^d	68.99 ± 0.22 ^e	82.79 ± 0.24 ^f	94.88 + 0.25 ^g	115.90 + 0.26 ¹¹	132.83 ±0.23 ^j	162.26 + 0.23- ¹	185.97 - 0.26 ^k	227.16 ±0.27 ¹

Means in the same raw followed by different superscripts differ significantly (P < 0.05; P < 0.01). Serum alanine kinase activity (LI. L⁻¹),² Hepatic cytosolic alanine kinase activity. Means in the same row followed by similar superscripts are not significantly different (P > 0.05).

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Table 4. Percent mortality and survival of *H. bidorsalis* juveniles fed with diets (38% crude protein) incorporated with different concentrations of unprocessed soyabean meal for 56 days

Duration (days)	← % Mortality					→ % Survival						
	% Incorporation of USBM					Control		% Incorporation of USBM				Control
	D ₁	D ₂	D ₃	D ₄	D ₅	D ₀	D ₁	D ₂	D ₃	D ₄	D ₅	D ₀
14	3.00	4.00	7.00	10.00	12.00	2.00	97.00	96.00	93.00	90.00	88.00	98.00
28	4.00	5.00	9.00	14.00	15.00	2.00	96.00	95.00	91.00	89.00	85.00	98.00
42	5.00	5.00	10.00	16.00	18.00	1.00	95.00	95.00	90.00	84.00	82.00	99.00
56	5.00	6.00	11.00	18.00	20.00	0.00	95.00	94.00	89.00	82.00	80.00	100.00